

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF USING HUMAN CAPITAL

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Abstract: In this article, under the influence of the development of information and communication technologies, the development of the global economy, the increase in the level of digitalization, in turn, ensures economic growth. This is where digitized human capital plays a major role, and relevant proposals have been developed accordingly.

Keywords: technology, digital economy, global economy, human capital, economic growth, knowledge, ability, development trends, human resources, integrated approach.

As a result of the rapid development of information and communication technologies in the 21st century, it has achieved a high economic growth rate at the level of the global economy and at the level of individual economies. During modern research, he paid attention to the issues of human capital utilization in service entities.

Through an integrated approach to the use of human capital, it can be observed that the demand for high-quality human capital is increasing. It can be seen from the modern researches that non-traditional knowledge, which is always directed, consists in identifying new patterns and trends of development, the events and processes that occur, establishing their relationships and assessing the influence of factors, and moving to the development stage depending on them. In the future, the task of effective use of human resources will be relevant, the capital that allows to increase labor productivity is to increase the potential of personnel by attracting existing ones to activate economic activity.

It is appropriate to consider ways of using human capital. To implement them, it is necessary to accumulate knowledge and skills that constitute direct capital, as

well as opportunities to capitalize it, that is, to increase the nature of production. At the same time, taking into account the income from the direct use of the human capital of the enterprise, evaluating the human capital, which has an individual character due to the uniqueness of each employee, is more appropriate to rely on the results of the expert's work, because it requires taking into account the characteristics of a particular employee. Therefore, with the help of human capital development methodology and its evaluation, an enterprise can determine its ability to create value beyond its financial and material assets.

For this reason, it is appropriate to clarify the knowledge of human capital theory, focusing on human capital in neo-Keynesian, institutional, neoclassical theories and other emerging private economic studies. The concept of human capital was a response to the expediency of science, it is one of the studies that work on the substantiation of the relationship between indicators of economic development and individual characteristics. Ideas classics economic ideas important roles intangible component reproductions A field that reflects a broad interpretation in management theory is human capital. V. Petty was one of the first to pay attention to human capital, an able-bodied person, because the term "human capital" did not exist yet, and put it into scientific circulation.

Thus, in 1676, in his political work, the arithmetician V. Petty analyzes the value of people and reflects the value that each person and all people recognize as the main productive force, which is more than twenty times the annual income they bring. Therefore, the value of the population in England is estimated at 520 million pounds, and the cost of each is 80 to 20 million pounds. It will be necessary to increase the role of human productive forces in the economy, which were only the first evaluation attempts in the works of V. Petty. Then L. Turov continues this doctrine and recognizes that when assessing value, he believed that human capital should be taken into account as a measure of human ability. However, he adds to his theory the measurement of innate ability, in the measurement of innate ability, a person and his talent, acquired skills, education, economic abilities are taken into

account in the composition of human capital. Thus, L. Turou measured human capital by its price, by which the production capacity is multiplied by their number. From the second half of the 20th century, scientific research continued on the concepts of the value of human capital. T. Schultz, G. Becker, J. Mintzer and other followers should be given special recognition for doing exactly this research. Thus, T. Schultz and G. From Becker's point of view, it is possible to show that it is measured by the form that serves as the main source of human capital, that there are opportunities for future income, satisfaction with the income of the employee and the accumulation of productive capacity through it.

T. Shults scientifically proved that human capital is the main engine and basis of the post-industrial economy, and for the first time takes into account costs when measuring the value of human capital, education as an important component of which justified the rate of economic growth and the future development path, individual costs of wages and education believed that encouragement was necessary. In this way, the theory of T. Shults showed that education costs have a two-factor structure, on the one hand, it returns the current income of the consumer of education, and on the other hand, it justified the accumulation of the employee's income through the payment of future wages.

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